

THE PURPOSE OF PRESERVING LIFE AND OFFSPRING SURVIVAL, A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN ISLAMIC AND WESTERN THOUGHT

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ABSTRACT

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Preserving life and preserving the human race is one of the essential supreme goals of all religions and laws and approved - in the sentence - by all systems and laws. This research paper seeks to discuss this great purpose from two aspects; The side of nothingness and the side of existence.

From the first aspect, scholars and thinkers from various walks of life endeavored to preserve human life from aggression by devastating wars and similar deadly diseases and famines.

On the other hand, theorizing was done to promote the human race by providing the basic needs of human beings and saving the human race from loss and corruption.

KEYWORDS:

Preservation of life, continuity of offspring, Islamic thought, Western thought.

INTRODUCTION

The modern era has witnessed many devastating wars that claimed the lives of millions of people and left devastating effects on all aspects of human life, which worried scientists and thinkers in the East and West and urged them to remind the central purposes of human existence.

The purpose of preserving life and the continuation of the offspring can be considered the first central goal from which the rest of the purposes for which humans were created originate. Therefore, any harm inflicted on it is inevitably the return of harm to other purposes belonging to it.

Hence the importance of this greatest goal was great, and the thinkers paid great attention to it. This article seeks to contribute to highlighting the efforts of these intellectuals from the Islamic and Western civilizations in defending human rights to live in peace and security so that he can carry out his function in life

First theme: life preservation purpose and the continuation of offspring from a non-existence perspective.

Every civilized community has necessary basic needs, namely, the need for peace and safety, which lead to self-preservation and the continuity of offspring that entail numerous benefits. Hence, wise people from different cultures and ethnicities insisted on the importance of peace that allows human beings to reach quality in surviving this life.

Furthermore, civilized societies devoted all efforts to warning against the danger of war on human beings; based on that, the famous English philosopher Francis Bacon AD 1626 claims that God has given us souls equal to the entire world. The great

represented in the reconstruction and reform of the land and development of its resources.

In this work, I tried to refer to the founding and explanatory texts in the Islamic heritage represented in the Holy Qur'an and the Prophet's Sunnah and the sayings of advanced and late Muslim scholars and thinkers.

It also relied on the Western heritage represented in the Bible and the opinions of philosophers from different ages and places, intending to find common grounds between the Islamic and Western approaches and benefit from the points of convergence between them in order to work on highlighting and developing them so that the largest possible number of people can be convinced; There is agreement and meeting that there is no difference or disunity, as is well known to the scholars.

lesson that a human being can learn from experience and life is that "the noblest and greatest lesson in life is that humans should not fight each other instead, they can challenge the obstacles that prevent him/her from surviving in the Mother Nature" (Durant,n.d).

Thus, a philosopher of the French Enlightenment, Voltaire, AD 1778, categorically proclaimed the war, despite the French victories of his era, he expressed: "War is the root of crimes and the greatest evil, and every country tries to be innocent and hide its crimes, yet any offense is punishable and unacceptable in peacetime, but if the war is declared, killing becomes permissible." (Voltaire, 1763)

In his philosophical lexicon, Voltaire concluded in his reflections on humans, "Humans needed thirty centuries to learn about their nature, and it may take unlimited time to learn about their soul. However, it takes just a moment to kill themselves". (Voltaire, 2006)

Oppositely, the Prussian (German) Emmanuel Kant AD 1804 explained war from a deeper perspective; in his bold philosophical project entitled "Project for lasting Peace," he focused on the wickedness of war. Accordingly, the war turns the country's resources, which are supposed to be addressed for education, citizens' awareness, people's health, and safety, into competition in manufacturing killing mechanisms and the acquisition of destruction equipment. Eventually, peace becomes worse than a short war because of the excessive armament of armies, which is at the nation's expense. (Kant, n.d)

Therefore, war leads to aggression and destruction; as John Locke stated in AD 1704, it is contrary to the law of creation, opposed to the law of Nature, and even worse. (Locke, 1823)

According to the English philosopher Herbert Spencer AD 1903: "war is similar to a cannibal, undoubtedly it is forbidden and prohibited, especially that justice cannot grow and prosper unless there is cooperation and harmony between people and less hostility".(Amin and Najib,1936)

Similarly, philosophers' and intellectuals' theories correspond to the Islamic vision of preserving life and protecting the offspring for human existence. The lord Allah said: "Verily, I am going to place (mankind) generations after generations on earth." [Surah Al-Baqara 30], meaning that humans are successors of each other and simultaneously successors of Allah on

earth, which honors the human race. God Almighty also stated: "O you who believe! Enter perfectly in Islam (by obeying all the rules and regulations of the Islamic religion) and follow not the footsteps of Shaitan (Satan). Verily! He is to you a plain enemy." [Surah Al-Baqara 206].

Second theme: The preservation of life and the continuation of the offspring from the existing perspective.

Civilization and human development strongly depend on social peace and food security. Allah said: "So let them worship (Allah) the Lord of this House (the Kaaba in Makkah). (He) Who has fed them against hunger and has made them safe from fear." [Surah Quraish 3-4]. Additionally, God states clearly in the Holy Quran about His blessing of security and peace on the people of Makkah: "Have they not seen that We have made (Makkah) a sanctuary secure and that men are being snatched away from all around them?" [Surah Al Ankaboot 67].

Even though humanity suffered from different shortcomings at the level of feeding throughout history, and all the wars and conflicts that have left many tragedies and sorrows, wise people from all over the world call for the need to intensify human efforts in order to live in peace and security for the sake of the human race continuity.

Therefore, modern Western thought has seriously considered this fundamental issue in the lives of peoples and Nations. Food, psychological and social security are among the basic needs upon which human society is based. John Locke says, "Whether we consider natural reason, which tells us that man, being once born, have a right to their preservation, meat and

drink, and such things as Nature affords for their subsistence. Or "revelation," which gives us an account of those grants God made of the world to Adam, and Noah and his sons." (Locke, 1823).

The provision of the necessary food and drink for human life takes ages because many basic food products require months to become edible. As a result, there was an urgent need for peace and security so that farmers could fulfill enough food for people; otherwise, famine would kill the people before the weapon.(Broadwell,1999).

Although food and drink represent the minimum in the basic needs scale, family and offspring preservation are crucial innate matters in societies. Dr. Thomas P. Alice states: "From a biological point of view, there are two main tasks that humans need to accomplish: First, is to survive and second, is procreation. The achievement of the latter task becomes effortless when the first one is accomplished. It is worth mentioning that humans have encountered numerous obstacles to surviving and procreating throughout evolutionary time. However, the most effective conducts in overcoming genetic barriers are those that have greater reproductive success and therefore better adaptive suitability." (Firman, 2015).

Marriage was thus recognized as an indispensable necessity for both animals and humans. Marriage is a divine power that plays a significant role in the continuation of offspring and the Reproduction of creatures on earth.

The German philosopher Schopenhauer considered marriage and Reproduction the only solution to survival from extinction and the survival of living beings; he said: "Reproduction is the ultimate purpose of

every organism and its strongest instinct; for only so can the will conquer death ".(Durant,n.d).

Humans are honored by the Creator thanks to their social relations, which are strongly tied by a moral bond at three levels. Firstly, spouses bond. Secondly, parents and children bond. Thirdly, family members bond; these three levels represent the essential unit of society. Allah said, "And Allah has made for you wives of your kind, and has made for you, from your wives, sons, and grandsons, and has bestowed on you good provision. Do they then believe in false deities and deny the Favour of Allah (by not worshipping Allah Alone)" [Surah Al-Nahl 72].

Civilized nations have maintained the Islamic view of marriage charter and the sacredness of human relationships. This view was disaffected only by humiliated people, while sages and gurus appreciated the relationship between the uterus.

The German philosopher Hegel AD 1831 confirmed: "Families that regulate the reproductive instinct by marriage are an essential social institution. Marriage ensures the proper upbringing of children; it is not only an emotional matter but also a sacred duty."(Amin and Najib,1936).

Yet, life is not limited to marriage and childbearing; it is even greater. Life is represented in the preservation of the offspring, not only from the interruption in the cessation of childbearing but also in the sense of the inability to pursue the successive function of humans, including reform, non-corruption, material development, and spiritual purification. Consequently, parents' duty is great, and their standing will remain preserved in all laws and sects.

CONCLUSION

God Almighty created humans to rehabilitate the earth, reform life's affairs, and develop its resources and bounties. However, these aspirations and goals will not be achieved for humanity unless the greater original objective is achieved: the preservation of life and the continuation of offspring.

Because of the great importance of this purpose, scholars and thinkers from various walks of life took care of it. They wrote books on it and gave lectures confirming its necessity for the integrity of human life and warning against the danger of neglecting it or belittling it.

And since man is a lot of forgetfulness, and since the instincts of domination and possession control him sometimes and direct his behavior at other times, it is necessary to remind him that those desires to enjoy blessings will not be fulfilled except with the realization of the original purpose, which is the right to life, which guarantees the possibility of benefiting from the rest of the other accessory rights. Therefore, these instincts and desires must be controlled and directed towards the preservation of life, the continuity of offspring, and the recourse to the rules of reason and logic in managing disputes and managing conflicts, so that humanity can lead a safe and reassuring life, which is the best way to advance and civilize humanity. Hence, this article calls for the intensification of efforts among those working in the various fields of knowledge in order to highlight the necessity of this greatest goal, emphasize its importance to human life in general, and constantly remind us of the danger of neglecting it amid the conflict that may be imposed by

the conflict of interests and different purposes.

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